

broken using boiling water. We studied the effect of boiling water treatment for varying times on the germinability of seeds of *S. rostrata*.

Welldeveloped seeds were selected, 50/set, and treated with 98 °C water for

15-180 s at intervals of 15 s. Treated seeds and untreated seeds were arranged on filter paper, placed in petri dishes, and moistened with distilled water. The germination test was carried out at room temperature (27-30 °C).

Treatment with boiling water increased germination from 4 to 78% with 75-s treatment (see table). Boiling water treatment beyond 75 s began to deform seeds. □

Crop management

Effect of sowing and planting method on rice yield

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Performance of two dwarf and one tall indica varieties—OR152-2-17, Pratap, and Mahsuri, all with 135-140 d duration—was compared under different sowing and planting methods during 1982 wet season.

Treatments were broadcast seeding with and without *beushaning* (operating narrow wooden plow in standing crop under 10-15 cm standing water 30-35 d after germination), line sowing sprouted seeds in puddled soil, line transplanting, and skip-row planting with full and 75% recommended fertilizer (80-40-40 kg NPK/ha). The design was split plot with varieties in the main plots and sowing or transplanting method as subplots, with

Influence of sowing and transplanting methods on yield and yield attributes of rice. Orissa, India, 1982 kharif.

Sowing or planting method	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Cost of cultivation (\$/ha)	Net profit (\$/ha)
Broadcast seeding	298	82	19.7	3.4	156	246
Broadcast seeding followed by <i>beushaning</i>	265	83	20.2	3.2	175	210
Line sowing sprouted seeds 15 cm apart	313	82	20.3	3.8	185	264
Transplanting at 15- × 10-cm spacing	344	83	20.0	4.3	232	285
Skip-row (3:1) transplanting with 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha	290	87	20.4	4.3	202	314
Skip-row (3: 1) transplanting with 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha	295	85	20.6	4.3	221	295
SE (m) ±	5	1	0.3	0.1	—	—
LSD (0.05)	16	3	ns	0.2	—	—

three replications.

Soil of the experimental site was sandy loam with pH 6.1. Total N content was 0.031%, 17.3 kg available P/ha, and 104 kg available K/ha.

The interaction between variety and planting method was not significant. Grain yields under normal line planting, skip-row planting with 75% normal fertilizer, and skip-row planting with

normal fertilizer were not statistically different (see table). Skip-row planting with 75% normal fertilizer produced the highest net profit, followed by skip-row planting with full fertilizer. These methods saved 25% of the cost seedlings or fertilizers. Broadcast seeding followed by *beushaning* produced the lowest grain yield and net profit, probably because of low plant population. □

Selecting rice varieties for double transplanting in flood-affected areas

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Large areas on the riverbanks in northeastern India frequently become flooded two to three times during the wet season, severely damaging the rice crop. Some farmers risk transplanting

rice in early Jul. If flooding comes late or is mild, the transplanted crop suffers least. Most farmers, however, do not want to risk transplanting early because they cannot afford to manage seedlings for retransplanting if the Jul crop is flooded. They usually transplant in Sep, when the chance of flooding ceases.

Two types of seedlings—conventional seedlings brought directly from the first nursery and kharuhan seedlings uprooted from the first nursery and transplanted closely in a second nursery—are transplanted. Seedlings of any available photoperiod-sensitive rice variety are used. The double-

transplanted crop gives yields higher than a single-transplanted crop.

We conducted a field trial on silty-clay loam soil at the Rajendra Agricultural University Farm, Pusa (Bihar) during wet season using six photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties—Janaki, BR8, T141, B14, C62-68, and Bakol (local check)—and three dates of transplanting—1 Sep, 16 Sep, and 1 Oct.

The trial was in a split-plot design, with date of transplanting in the main plot and varieties in subplots, with three replications. Kharuhan seedlings (30 d in first nursery + 45 d in the second) were